

Non-alcoholic steatohepatitis and animal models: Understanding the human disease

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ABSTRACT

Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease includes a broad spectrum of liver abnormalities ranging from simple steatosis to non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH), which can progress to cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma. Patients with primary NASH have the metabolic (or insulin resistance) syndrome, condition typically associated with obesity, diabetes, hyperlipidemia and hypertension. To understand the mechanisms implicated in development of NASH, animal models of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease have been generated. These have greatly improved our understanding of some of the aspects of this disease. The challenge now is to identify the common mechanisms between the animal models and humans, which could eventually lead to a better prognosis and development of novel therapeutic strategies.

Keywords Liver, NASH, Animal models

INTRODUCTION

Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is a clinical pathological term that develops in the absence of alcohol abuse and that includes a spectrum of alterations that range from simple accumulation of fat in the liver exceeding 5–10% by weight (steatosis), to non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH) and advanced fibrosis which can lead to cirrhosis, liver failure and hepatocellular carcinoma. NAFLD is nowadays the leading cause for liver dysfunction and cirrhosis, with a prevalence of 20–30% in the western and U.S. population, respectively, and reaching levels as high as 75–100% in obese (BMI \geq 30) and morbidly obese (BMI \geq 40) people (Bedogni et al., 2005; Farrel and Larter, 2006).

Nowadays NAFLD is considered the hepatic manifestation of the metabolic syndrome (MS). MS refers to a cluster of features including obesity, glucose intolerance or diabetes, dyslipidemia and hypertension. Around 90% of NAFLD patients have at least one feature of MS and about 33% have the full diagnosis. MS has been also associated with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS), obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) and cardiovascular disease. Several reports also suggest that patients with PCOS and OSA require careful hepatic evaluation.

Most of the NAFLD patients are diagnosed by symptoms including fatigue, hepatomegaly or abnormal serum concentrations of aspartate transaminase (AST) and alanine transaminase (ALT). Around 80% of patients with NAFLD are, however, asymptomatic. The only reliable method for diagnosing fatty liver and/or NASH is percutaneous liver biopsy (Adams and Angulo, 2006). Histological abnormalities include macro- and micro-vesicular steatosis in NAFLD patients, and macro-vesicular or a mix between micro- and macro-vesicular steatosis with mild lobular inflammation in NASH patients. Ballooned hepatocytes and pericellular fibrosis

in acinar zone 3 are also observed. Megamitochondria and Mallory's hyaline bodies are more commonly reported in ASH, but may be observed in NASH.

Here, we describe some of most important pathogenic mechanisms in steatosis and steatohepatitis and the contribution of the most used animal models to the field. We discuss the features for each animal model including pathology, pathogenic mechanisms and, limitations and merits in relation to human pathology (Table 1). We also describe the current therapeutical strategies in the treatment of NAFLD (Table 2).

Pathogenesis of liver steatosis

Accumulation of fat in the liver results mainly from an excessive delivery of free fatty acids (FFA) from visceral adipose tissue (VAT) into the liver, and from a misbalance in de novo lipid synthesis and catabolism in hepatocytes.

Visceral adipose tissue

Increase in VAT mass has been associated with obesity, insulin resistance (IR) and NAFLD. FFA, hormones (e.g. leptin, adiponectin and resistin) and adipocytokines (e.g. TNF- α and IL-6) are released from VAT into the portal vein and delivered into the liver. FFA and TNF- α play a key role in liver steatosis and IR development during MS (Fig. 1).

TNF- α mRNA expression in adipose tissue and TNF- α plasma levels are increased in IR obese humans and in ob/ob mice. Ob/ob and diet-induced obesity mice lacking TNF- α or its receptor are protected against IR development. In adipose tissue, TNF- α -mediated IR reduces the inhibitory effect of insulin on hormone sensitive lipase (HSL), increasing lipolysis and the release of FFA into the systemic circulation. Secreted TNF- α is also able to enhance the synthesis of FA translocases in hepatocytes, increasing FA uptake (Anstee and Goldin, 2006).

FFA and TNF- α blocks the insulin receptor activity, preventing the activation of PI3K (phosphoinositide 3-kinase) and other downstream signalling events. Tyrosine phosphorylation of insulin receptor substrate (IRS) is the general mechanism of insulin action. Downregulation of IRS signalling caused by serine phosphorylation appears to be the underlying mechanism of FFA and TNF- α -mediated IR (Fig. 1).

De novo lipid synthesis

Peripheral IR impairs glucose uptake from blood into skeletal muscle and adipose tissue, whereas liver IR impairs the anti-glucogenic effect of insulin, increasing the hepatic synthesis of glucose. Taken together, peripheral and liver IR induce an increase in glucose levels. To ameliorate this hyperglucemic state, IR subjects increase insulin secretion and reduce insulin clearance. These high levels of glucose and insulin synergistically induce the conversion of glucose into FA through de novo lipid synthesis (Fig. 1).

Glucose activates the nuclear transcription factor carbohydrate response element-binding protein (ChREBP), which upregulates the conversion of glucose into pyruvate by increasing the expression of l-pyruvate kinase (L-PK), which is one of the rate limiting enzymes of glycolysis. ChREBP also increases transcription of the lipogenic enzymes acetyl CoA carboxylase (ACC) and fatty acid synthase (FAS) genes (Denechaud et al., 2008). The transcription of these genes is also increased by the transcription factor SREBP-1c (sterol regulatory element-binding proteins 1c), which is upregulated by high insulin levels (Dentin et al., 2005). Thus, both glucose and insulin, via ChREBP and SREBP-1c, respectively, synergistically promote the conversion of pyruvate into FA.

Ob/ob mice characterized by hyperglycemia and hyperinsulinemia have marked increase in ChREBP and SREBP-1c gene expression and nuclear localization. Indeed, liver-specific inhibition of ChREBP in ob/ob mice improved hyperglycemia and hyperinsulinemia, decreasing plasma concentration of FFA and triglycerides (Denechaud et al., 2008).

Another transcription factor implicated in de novo FA synthesis is peroxisome proliferators-activated receptor γ (PPAR γ). PPAR γ is normally expressed in high levels in adipose tissue and at very low levels in liver. In adipose tissue, PPAR γ activity increases insulin sensitivity and FA uptake, and promotes adipocyte differentiation and the expression of proteins involved in FA synthesis. PPAR γ also limits the FA influx into the liver. Mice deficient in liver-specific PPAR γ are protected against the development of steatosis, suggesting a role of hepatic PPAR γ in liver fat accumulation (Gavrilova et al., 2003).

IR is associated with adipose tissue inflammation, which modifies hormone secretion. Adiponectin is an anti-lipogenic hormone that stimulates mitochondrial β -oxidation by the activation of the AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) in the liver. Adiponectin has also anti-inflammatory properties, blocking the synthesis and release of TNF- α from macrophages within adipose tissue in obesity. Adiponectin levels are decreased in patients with obesity, IR, type-2 diabetes and NAFLD. In NASH patients, adiponectin serum levels are further reduced compared to patients with steatosis alone (Hui et al., 2004). Administration of recombinant adiponectin to ob/ob mice attenuates serum ALT levels and drastically reduces hepatic steatosis, been considered a promising candidate for the treatment of obesity-associated metabolic syndromes.

Taken together these data point out the importance of IR in NAFLD development. Recently, mice with liver-specific deletion of PTEN were generated and they mimic some of the histological evidences of human NASH (Table 1). However, PTEN deletion causes insulin hypersensitivity, the complete opposite of NASH pathology, increasing liver fatty acid synthesis with moderate increase of SREBP-1c and its targets. More studies should be done to understand the pathogenesis of NASH in this model (Horie et al., 2004).

Decreased FFA β -oxidation and FFA disposal via VLDL export

Decreased lipid disposal via β -oxidation or VLDL export are only moderate causes of FA accumulation in the liver. The rate limiting step of mitochondrial β -oxidation is the transfer of FA into the mitochondria, regulated by carnitine palmitoyltransferase I (CPT-I). The increased production of malonyl-CoA during lipid synthesis inhibits CPT-I. However, increased CPT-I hepatic expression partly results from the activation of the nuclear transcription factor PPAR α by FFA. In addition, PPAR α modulates the expression of enzymes of mitochondrial and peroxisomal β -oxidation (Kallwitz et al., 2008; Leclercq, 2007).

FFA are esterified into TG and then exported as VLDL. Failure of synthesis and secretion of VLDL can further contribute to TG accumulation in the liver (Tarantino et al., 2007). Decreased VLDL secretion has been observed in db/db mice fed with a methionine choline deficient (MCD) diet (Rinella et al., 2008). In humans, however, there is only one study suggesting that VLDL trafficking is impaired in NASH (Charlton et al., 2002).

Pathogenesis of liver steatohepatitis

In 1998 was proposed the two-hit model of NASH pathogenesis (Day and James, 1998); a first hit (steatosis) increases the sensitivity of the liver to secondary insults. Cytokines, mitochondrial dysfunction, oxidative stress and lipid peroxidation are the main “second hits” in the induction of primary NASH (Fig. 2).

NASH patients exhibit mitochondrial abnormalities and dys-function. Mitochondrial dysfunction is mainly the result of IR and excess FFA (lipotoxicity). Mitochondrial impairment causes enhanced reactive nitrogen species (ROS) production initiating lipid peroxidation and increasing ROS. Furthermore, lipid peroxidation of mitochondrial membranes and damage of mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) can contribute to the impairment of mitochondrial function and perpetuate the ROS generation.

Oxidative stress was increased in patients with NASH compared to NAFLD and normal control subjects (Sanyal et al., 2001). Increased lipid peroxidation has been reported in livers from ob/ob mice, rats fed with an MCD diet, and MAT1A-KO mice (Table 1). Deficient FA oxidation decreases energy substrates contributing to organ dysfunction and injury (Koteish and Diehl, 2001).

FA and TNF- α are able to induce UCP-2 expression in primary hepatocytes, and an increase in UCP-2 expression has been observed in livers from NASH patients, ob/ob mice and in rats fed with an MCD diet. UCP-2 is a mitochondrial inner membrane protein that mediates proton leak across the inner membrane by uncoupling substrates oxidation (such as FA) from ATP synthesis. Recently, it has been found that induced UCP-2-lack in ob/ob mice improve serum ALT levels, hepatocellular necrosis and liver ATP levels after ischemia. Livers from MAT1A-KO mice over-express UCP-2 (Table 1), showing ATP depletion and impaired liver regeneration after partial hepatectomy (Chen et al., 2004). Also, primary NASH patients show decrease activity of respiratory chain complexes and have acute ATP depletion after fructose challenge. Taken together these studies suggest that even though UCP-2 expression lowers the redox pressure, it compromises the liver capacity to respond to additional acute energy demand.

FFA induces the activation of CYP2E1 and CYP4A isoforms, leading to an increase in ROS production and uncoupling mitochondrial respiration. Insulin down-regulates CYP2E1 expression, and IR potentially explains its upregulation during NASH (Moncion et al., 2002). Increased CYP2E1 activity has also been described in rats fed with MCD (Anstee and Goldin, 2006) diet and in MAT1A-KO mice (Martinez-Chantar et al., 2002). CYP2E1-induced expression by pirazole in ob/ob mice was shown to potentiate liver injury (Dey et al., 2007). CYP2E1 over-expression has been observed in morbidly obese humans with NAFLD and in NASH patients.

Decrease in antioxidants defence

S-adenosylmethionine (SAdMe) is the major methyl donor in liver and is a precursor to glutathione (GSH). The decrease in SAdMe synthesis, observed in livers from animals fed with MCD diet and in MAT1A-KO mice, leads to decreased hepatic GSH levels, impairing the antioxidant defence against ROS (Mato et al., 2008). Recent studies suggest that SAdMe could protect against and also reverse CYP2E1-induced liver damage in ob/ob mice (Dey et al., 2007). SAdMe is commercially available and its potential therapeutical use in NASH is commented in Table 2.

Glycine N-methyltransferase (GNMT) is the enzyme responsible for the catabolism of excess SAdMe in the liver. Recently, three young individuals with mutations in the GNMT gene were identified. They have liver disease with elevated levels of plasma SAdMe, methionine, and serum transaminases. GNMT-KO mice also have increased serum levels of methionine, SAdMe and transaminases, and spontaneously develop steatosis, steatohepatitis, fibrosis and HCC (Martinez-Chantar et al., 2008).

The observation that both SAdMe depletion in MAT1A-KO mice and SAdMe excess in GNMT-KO mice can lead to similar liver pathology is intriguing. However, the molecular

mechanisms are different in the two models. While hepatic SAME depletion leads to spontaneous oxidative stress, supra-physiological SAME levels leads to aberrant hypermethylation of DNA and histones resulting in epi-genetic modulation of critical carcinogenic pathways such as the Ras and JAK/STAT pathways in the liver (Martinez-Chantar et al., 2008).

Pathogenesis of fibrosis

Lipid peroxidation and ROS induce inflammation as well as hepatocyte necrosis and apoptosis (Fig. 2). Phagocytosis of these apoptotic bodies by hepatic stellate cell (HSC) has been shown to have a role in HSC activation and fibrogenesis development in vivo and in vitro. In inflammatory cells, ROS causes NF κ B activation, which induces the production of inflammatory cytokines, such as TNF- α (Marra et al., 2008) leading to neutrophil chemotaxis. In addition, ROS and products of lipid peroxidation can directly activate HSCs, which results in release of pro-fibrogenic cytokines (TGF- β) and collagen. Finally, other factors like leptin (a pro-fibrogenic factor) can contribute to fibrosis development activating the JAK/STAT pathway. Indeed, ob/ob mice, that show leptin deficiency, are protected against the development of hepatic fibrosis.

Therapy and concluding remarks

The current therapeutical strategies in NAFLD treatment are mostly directed toward correction of the risk factors (Torres and Harrison, 2008). In Table 2 the main strategies are described, including their modes of action, effects and merits.

The different animal models studied so far have given us invaluable information of some of the mechanisms involved in NAFLD development and have helped us to identify therapeutic targets. However, it is critical to develop animal models that fit more accurately the metabolic changes of NAFLD in humans. For instant, the use of a combined animal model looks promising. Indeed the combination of MCD and HF diet depicts the features of steatohepatitis as well as obesity and IR, which are observed frequently in NASH patients (Cong et al., 2008).

So far, most of the animal data available has been generated from male animals. NAFLD is a disease that predominantly affects men and post-menopausal women. A better understanding of the mechanisms underlying the sex-associated differences in NASH may help in the diagnosis, prevention and treatment of the disease.

Finally, the development of novel techniques such as high throughput analysis may help to identify new markers for NASH diagnosis. Despite the enormous amount of data provided by platforms of genetic expression analysis, little information of metabolites is available. Metabolites are the last step in the biological processes initiated with gene expression. The study of metabolome in different animal models should be a very efficient method to identify possible serum biomarkers useful for diagnosis, and to distinguish the responsive and non-responsive patients to a specific drug.

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Table 1. Pathology and pathogenic mechanisms of several animal models of NASH. Limitations and merits in relation to human pathology.

Spontaneous or induced genetic models				
	Definition	Model characteristics	Mechanisms	Comments
Increased lipid import/synthesis	db/db and ob/ob mice, fa/fa rats ob/ob mice: leptin-deficient due to a spontaneous mutation in the leptin gene. db/db mice and fa/fa rats: leptin-resistant due to a mutation in the leptin receptor gene, having similar phenotype than ob/ob mice (Anstee and Goldin, 2006).	Hyperphagia. Obese and diabetic. IR with hyperinsulinemia, hyperglycemia and hyperlipidemia. Develop fatty livers spontaneously. Increased mass of white adipose tissue. Leptin treatment reduces food consumption, body weight, hyperinsulinemia, hyperglycemia and also partial regression of hepatic steatosis.	Increased expression of TNF- α . Hepatocyte nuclear accumulation of SREBP-1c and ChREBP. Increased liver expression of microsomal enzymes β -oxidation and UCP-2. Expression of PPAR γ in livers. Present low levels of adiponectin, but administration of recombinant adiponectin improves serum ALT and reduces hepatic steatosis. Exposure to secondary insults increases hepatic production of ROS and TNF- α .	DV: Leptin gene mutations are not prevalent in humans. These models do not develop spontaneously steatohepatitis or liver fibrosis. AV: ob/ob mice phenotype simulates the human condition of MS in many aspects, making ob/ob mice the most used model to study the risk factors in NAFLD.
	PTEN-KO Liver-specific induced knock-out of a phosphatase and tensin homolog. PTEN antagonizes PI3K/AKT signalling pathway (Horie et al., 2004).	Hepalomegaly and fatty liver. Increased TG, cholesterol and serum transaminases. Increased FA synthesis in the liver (no by uptake). Increased glycogen synthesis. Mallory bodies, mild fibrogenic changes, lobular inflammatory cells (steatohepatitis and fibrosis). Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) . Different fatty liver phenotype from that of hyperinsulinemic and IR models.	Induction of hepatic lipogenesis High levels of PPAR γ and its downstream targets (adipsin, adipose binding protein aP2, adiponectin). Moderate increase of SREBP-1c and its targets (FAS, ACC). Induced genes involved in β -oxidation. Hepatocytes with no PTEN gene express adipocyte-specific genes.	DV: Increased levels of adiponectin. Insulin hypersensitivity (reduced serum insulin levels). Hypoleptinemia. AV: The histological phenotype resembles human NASH.
Affected methionine metabolism	MAT1A-KO Liver-specific induced knock-out of the MAT1A gene, leading to a decrease in SAMe synthesis (Martinez-Chantler et al., 2002; Mato et al., 2008).	Reduced levels of serum SAMe. Plasmatic hypermethionemia and hyperglycemia with normal insulin levels. Elevated hepatic TG levels. Increased liver weight. Steatosis (3 months old), steatohepatitis (8 months old) and HCC (18 months old). At 3 months old is more susceptible to choline deficient diet-induced fatty liver.	Reduction of liver SAMe and GSH levels. High expression of CYP2E1 and UCP-2 Increased expression of serum malondialdehyde. PPAR γ upregulation. At 3 months old MAT1A-KO are predispose to CCl ₄ -induced hepatotoxicity, due to CYP2E1 upregulation.	DV: Not IR. AV: A study performed from 2000 to 2007 showed 1/28163 incidence in newborn, that were heterozygous for the dominant mutation R264H in the MAT1A gene. MAT1A-KO mouse is a good model to examine the consequences of chronic SAMe deficiency, a situation that likely occurs in patients with advanced liver disease.
	GNMT-KO Induced knock-down of the glycine N-methyltransferase (GNMT) gene that produces high levels of SAMe (Martinez-Chantler et al., 2008).	Elevated levels of serum transaminases, methionine and SAMe. The ratio of SAMe/SAH (S-adenosyl homocysteine) is highly increased in livers of homozygous knock-out mice. Develop liver steatosis, fibrosis (3 months old), and HCC (8 months old).	Hypermethylation of DNA and histones resulting in epigenetic modulation of critical carcinogenic pathways such as the Ras and JAK/STAT pathways. Differential expression of key genes involved in liver lipid homeostasis and oxidative stress at 3 and 8 months (unpublished).	DV: Neither obese nor IR. AV: GNMT is absent in hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), messenger RNA (mRNA) levels are significantly lower in livers of patients at risk of developing HCC, and GNMT has been proposed to be a tumor-susceptibility gene for liver cancer.
Environmental models				
	Definition	Model characteristics	Mechanisms	Comments
Increased lipid uptake	HFD Wild Type animals fed diet with high levels of saturated or unsaturated fat and/or carbohydrates and/or proteins.	These models are used to study the risk factors related with obesity and IR. Variability of the results depending on genetic backgrounds, sex, age of animal and by the fat diet (composition and days of treatment) (Nishikawa et al., 2007).		
			Rat models	
		HFD (71% fat). Mitochondria abnormalities. IR. Inflammation with high hepatic concentrations of collagen (early fibrosis). Steatosis and steatohepatitis (Lieber et al., 2004)	Abnormal mitochondria and inflammation. Increased TNF- α and CYP2E1 mRNA and proteins. Lipid peroxidation was elevated (4-hydroxynonenal).	DV: Rats are not obese. No high levels of ALT.
		Mouse models		
	*C57BL/6 and/or 129S6/SvEvTac strains with HFD. Steatosis. Accumulation of body fat. High levels of circulating leptin that induces leptin resistance and hyperphagia (Winzel and Ahren, 2004; Biddinger et al., 2005).	Increased expression of Stearoyl-CoA, SREBP-1c and SRBP-2.	DV: When ageing, C57BL/6 spontaneously develops obesity, hyperinsulinemia and glucose intolerance independently of diet.	
	*C57BL/6 with HFD by intragastric overfeeding. IR, increased visceral fat and obesity. Increased serum ALT. Glucose intolerance, hyperglycemia, hyperinsulinemia, hyperleptinemia. Steatohepatitis (Deng et al., 2005).	Not increased CYP2E1 expression. High CYP4A expression. Increased expression of SREBP-1c, PPAR γ and Liver X Receptor α . Reduced expression of PPAR α . Decreased levels of adiponectin.	DV: To accomplish these experiments is needed a very specific training and equipment. AV: Resembles the histopathologic and pathogenic features of NASH.	
Reduced β -oxidation	MCD Diet deficient in methyl groups (choline, methionine, folates) (London and George, 2007).	Spontaneously develop hepatic steatosis, inflammation and fibrosis. Severely depleted of hepatic antioxidants (as reduced GSH and SAMe) increasing oxidative stress.	Mitochondrial DNA damage with impaired mitochondrial β -oxidation and ROS production. Induction of CYP2E1. Apoptosis. Hepatic stellate cells activation. Extracellular matrix component deposition.	DV: Do not replicate the pathogenesis of human NASH and the histological distribution of steatosis differs from the NASH pattern in humans. Not IR and low plasma TG. Reduced liver weight/body ratio and cachectic. AV: Used to study the importance of oxidative stress and mitochondrial dysfunction in the pathogenesis of hepatic steatosis, inflammation and fibrosis. Used to evaluate specific dietary interventions and antioxidants in a mouse model of steatohepatitis.
Diet combined	mHFD (HFD+ MCD) Modified high-fat diet (lower methionine and choline and higher fat content) (Cong et al., 2008).	Obesity, dyslipidemia, IR. Increased hepatic TG. Elevated serum ALT. Develop steatosis, inflammation and fibrosis.	Increased expression of PPAR γ , aP2 and CD36. Suppression of the expression for PPAR α and CPT-1 α .	AV: Characteristics very similar to the general clinical features of human NASH. Model very useful to study both the risk factors and the oxidative stress damage related with human NASH.

The C57BL/6 mouse strain contains a spontaneous mutation on a gene (nicotinamide nucleotide transhydrogenase) that induces glucose intolerance (Toye et al., 2005). DV: Disadvantages when animal models are compared with humans, AV: Advantages when animal models are compared with humans.

Table 2. Therapeutical strategies in the treatment of NAFLD.

TREATMENT	MECHANISM OF ACTION	EFFECTS	ADVANTAGES & DISADVANTAGES
EXERCISE AND DIET (Clark, 2006)	Correct the risk factors associated with NAFLD.	Diet: In the setting of obesity, moderate weight loss (6%), improves IR and hepatic steatosis. Diet+Exercise: Improvement in serum ALT, hepatic steatosis and fasting glucose.	Ideal composition of the diets, total calorie intake and optimal exercise regime need better definition.
SURGICAL THERAPIES FOR WEIGHT LOSS IN MORBIDLY OBESE (Dixon 2007)	Correct obesity, and other risk factors associated with NAFLD.	Jejunioileal bypass induces dramatic weight loss. Adjustable gastric banding induces an average of 34 Kg weight loss, improving hepatic steatosis, inflammation and fibrosis. Roux-en-Y gastric bypass induces an average of 52 Kg weight loss, improving hepatic steatosis, inflammation and fibrosis.	Exacerbates steatohepatitis. They are more tolerated than Jejunioileal bypass, improving MS, IR, and hepatic histology.
WEIGHT LOSS MEDICATIONS (Torres and Harrison 2008)	Reversible inhibitor of gastric and pancreatic lipase, correcting obesity.	Orlistat: After 9 month's treatment, induces a 9% of body weight reduction, improving serum AST and ALT, hepatic steatosis and necroinflammation.	Improvement in fibrosis not always observed. Other weight loss medications are under investigation. More trials are needed to study the advantages against diet and exercise.
INSULIN SENSITIZING MEDICATIONS (Caldwell et al. 2006) (Kallwitz et al. 2008) (Gavrilova et al. 2003)	Thiazolidinediones (TZDs), PPAR γ agonist. Biguanide (Metformin), AMPK activator that decreases hepatic gluconeogenesis, improving insulin sensitivity and limiting TG production.	PPAR γ up-regulates adiponectin. Rosiglitazone in type 2 diabetic patients improves IR and transaminases and hepatic steatosis. Pioglitazone increases insulin sensitivity, improves serum ALT, hepatic steatosis and inflammation. Metformin improves hepatic steatosis and inflammation in steatotic animal models. Metformin in humans improve insulin sensitivity and serum ALT, without an improvement in fibrosis and necroinflammation. Metformin + low calorie diet + N-acetylcysteine: improves hepatic steatosis and fibrosis in patients with NASH.	There are evidences from animal models that TZDs may exert anti-fibrotic effects in the liver. However Pioglitazone effect on fibrosis is still controversial. TZDs therapy has side effects, such as weight gain, bone loss and increase risk of congestive heart failure and cardiovascular events. The effectiveness of Metformin alone in the improvement of fibrosis and necroinflammation is still controversial.
FIBRATES (Lecclercq et al. 2007)	PPAR α agonist.	Treatment with fibrate of MCD diet-feed mice, induces a decrease in fatty liver, level of ROS and oxidative stress injury, and prevents the inflammatory response and fibrosis. In humans, fibrate treatment lowers serum TG, but has not significant effects on hepatic steatosis or steatohepatitis.	The lack of effect in humans has been explained by the fact that humans express much lower hepatic PPAR α than rodents, and that the rate limiting enzymes in β -oxidation are not regulated solely by PPAR α .
ANTIOXIDANTS (Adams and Angulo 2008) (McClain et al. 2004) (Dey et al. 2007) (Mato et al. 2008)	Vitamin E (Tocopherol). S-Adenosylmethionine (SAME) is a metabolic precursor of GSH. Betaine is a metabolic precursor of SAME.	<i>In vitro</i> studies demonstrate that cytokine production can be inhibited and collagen production attenuated. Vitamin E improve serum ATL and IR. Decreased SAME concentrations are observed in multiple forms of experimental liver injury, including NAFLD. In animal studies exogenous SAME corrected hepatic deficiencies of SAME and GSH. SAME-treated subjects with alcoholic liver disease have been shown to decrease the need for liver transplantation and improve survival. Betaine supplements improve aminotransferase activity and liver histology in patients with NASH.	A recent RCT of vitamin E combined with vitamin C in NASH patients found not overall improvement in hepatic fibrosis score compared with placebo. Larger studies did not find vitamin E to be helpful. SAME is commercially available, with potential therapeutic efficacy in NASH. However trials in NASH patients are needed to study its potential beneficial effect. The results from GNM-T-KO mice, however, suggest that SAME levels should be tightly regulated. These results need to be confirmed in long-term prospective trials.

Fig. 1. Development of hepatic steatosis. Obesity is associated with an increase in TNF- α synthesis by VAT. TNF- α induces IR in VAT by increasing lipolysis and FA release into circulation. FFA and TNF- α are delivered into the liver, inducing liver IR. In the liver, TNF- α -induced increase of IKK13, PKC or JNK activity mediates IRS serine phosphorylation, FFA also contributes to liver IR by the activation of PKC-delta, which increase serine phosphorylation of IRS 1 and 2. In NAFLD patients, it has been estimated that 60% of FFA delivered into the liver arise from adipose tissue, 10% from diet and a 30% from de novo lipid synthesis. IR promotes hyperinsulinemia and hyperglucemia. Glucose and insulin synergistically induce the conversion of glucose into FA through de novo lipid synthesis, controlling the expression of critical enzymes of glycolysis and lipid synthesis through ChREBP and SREBP, respectively. FFA are also activators of PPAR α , a nuclear transcription factor controlling the expression of CPT-I, the rate limiting enzyme of FA import into the mitochondria. PPAR α also activates oxidizing enzymes of peroxisomal and mitochondrial- β -oxidation. Together, these pathways contribute to increase FFA oxidation.

Fig. 2. Development of hepatic steatohepatitis and fibrosis. Increase in FA oxidation induces ROS generation. This results in mitochondrial membrane lipid peroxidation, mtDNA and protein damage, leading to mitochondrial dysfunction. ROS diminishes also the antioxidant defence by decreasing GSH levels. FFA, TNF- α and ROS upregulate UCP-2 expression, uncoupling FA oxidation from ATP synthesis and decreasing ATP levels. Taken together these lead to hepatocyte death. Furthermore, ROS and lipid peroxidation products induce HSC activation and proinflammatory response from Kupffer cells, contributing to the inflammatory process and to fibrosis development.